

Resilience Capacity and the Determinants of Rural Household Food Security in Conflict Zones: Lessons from Nigeria**Ojo Idowu OLADEJI¹, Ajayi TEMITAYO², Atenchong Talleh NKOBOU³**

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Abstract

It is evident that about 68.65%% of the chronically undernourished people resides in countries plagued with conflict, and this condition is exacerbated by climate-related shocks, which is the case of North- East Nigeria. Against this backdrop, this study determines the level of food insecurity, food resilience capacity, and the determinant factors among rural household in Borno State, Nigeria, using 160 sampled secondary data from General Household Survey (GHS), conducted by the Nigeria National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) and the World Bank (WB), collected in 2018-2019. Key findings revealed that 44% of the household in the study area are food insecure with an average food poverty intensity of 0.441, while falling short of the population's mean percapita food expenditure in the study area by 19% at P_{a1} , and requiring a minimum of about ₦ 53328 to escape this vicious food insecurity embargo, while further analysis on the severity of poverty (P_{a2}) showed that this 43% food insecure suffers an average food intensity of 0.6273 and also falls short of the population's mean per capita food expenditure in the study area by 27% poverty severity level P_{a2} found significant at 5% probability level. The result of the Gini coefficient analysis revealed a high food consumption expenditure inequality margin of 0.83798 among the household in the study area. The Tobit regression shows that access to aid by household negatively influences food poverty, alongside years of formal education, and found significant at 1% probabilistic level respectively. Research study-based finding polices were also proffered.

Key words: Food security, Resilience, Conflict, Northeast Nigeria.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Boko Haram insurgencies have displaced thousands of Nigerians since 2010, forcing many farmers to flee their farms for safety (Ochonu, 2026). It is predicted that around 381.4 million of the 650.3 million chronically undernourished people in 2019 come from nations ravaged by violence, which is generally exacerbated by climate-related shocks (Food and Agriculture Organization, International Fund for Agricultural Development, United Nations Children's Fund, World Food Programme, and World Health Organization, 2021). In addition, thousands of people have died throughout the conflict and millions have been forced from their homes (Adelaja & George, 2019). Social, economic, and human growth are severely harmed by shocks and strains including political unrest, natural disasters, pandemics, and conflicts (Kerr *et al.*, 2026; Von Einsiedel *et al.* 2017; Schillinger *et al.* 2020; Qayyum, Anjum, and Sabir 2021; Menton *et al.* 2021; Hamoodi 2021; Okunlola and Okafor 2020; George, Adelaja, and Awokuse 2021), leading to slow progress towards achieving the SDGs set by the United Nations.

This study focuses on the damage of farm infrastructure, including irrigation and storage structures, and the kidnapping of farmers in order to attack agricultural production in Brono State, Nigeria. Brono state is located in the North Eastern part of Nigeria. Nigeria is one nation that has long experienced both internal strife and food shortages (Gråby, 2021). In the Lake Chad region, which makes up the majority of northeastern Nigeria, an estimated 80–90% of people rely on agriculture, fishing, and cattle for their livelihoods and food security (FAO, 2017). This implies that conflict might seriously harm the area by interfering with agriculture, leaving millions of rural households behind and possibly sparking more conflicts and instability in the future. About 9.1 million people are impacted by the present Boko Haram insurgency in Borno, Adamawa, and Yobe, the three most afflicted states in Nigeria's northeastern region (Young *et al.*, 2021). Due to delayed harvest seasons and higher food costs, food insecurity is a manifestation of the conflict's effects (FAO, 2015). According to FAO (2017), the conflict's effects on agriculture in Northeast Nigeria alone are projected to be worth USD 3.7 billion. Through waves of bombings, kidnappings, and killings, Boko Haram, a militant Islamist group, has wreaked havoc in Nigeria with the intention of overthrowing the current government without democracy and establishing Sharia law (UNICEF, 2022). Approximately 80% of Boko Haram's 2002 assaults in Nigeria between 2009 and 2016 occurred in the northeastern states of Borno, Yobe, and Adamawa (ACLED, 2017; Cross, 2025). Although Boko Haram's declared goal does not prevent the destruction of the agricultural sector, their actions do, as attacks impact rural households both directly and indirectly in addition to their means of subsistence.

Evidence from Nigerian conflict zones points to detrimental effects on agricultural output. For instance, Nigeria's wheat production fell significantly by 20% in 2016 compared to the year before (Awodola and Oboshi, 2015). The production of other important crops in the Northeast, including as cotton, legumes like cowpeas and groundnuts, vegetables like tomatoes, onions, and peppers, and grains like millet, sorghum, and rice, also significantly decreased (Kulei, 2020). During the crisis, Borno state's yearly grain flows with other states decreased from 300,000 tons in the fourth quarter of 2010 to roughly 100,000 tons in the second quarter of 2014 (Sidney, Zummo, and Kwajafa, 2017). By limiting the availability of labor, limiting access to land and other inputs, and undermining a number of social and economic support networks, conflict lowers agricultural output (Serneels and Verpoorten 2015; Verwimp and Muoz-Mora 2018). In addition to raising costs and depriving households of their potential food security status, this has implications for increased food scarcity or supply deficit. More than half of household income is spent on food in developing nations like Nigeria, making the impoverished extremely susceptible to abrupt price changes that could push them into poverty or obstruct efforts to reduce it (Badmus, 2025). The Nigerian government has therefore undertaken a number of initiatives to reduce terrorist-related activity in the northeastern region.

During the crisis, Borno State's yearly grain flow to and from other states decreased from 300,000 tons in the fourth quarter of 2010 to 100,000 tons in the second quarter of 2014 (Sidney, Hayatudeen, and Kwajafa, 2017). According to Van Den Hoek (2017), the state military, regional paramilitary, or Boko Haram's physical access restrictions to fields are the reasons behind the region's declining agricultural output. Young children who are exposed to the Boko Haram insurgency are more likely to experience morbidity and mortality (Dunn 2018). According to Dunn (2018), if there had been no conflict in Northeast Nigeria, the probability of childhood wasting would have been 13% lower.

George (2020) found in their study, "The Boko Haram conflict and food insecurity: Does resilience capacity matter?" Using data from the World Bank and Nigeria's National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) from 2010 to 2016 and a non-parametric difference-in-differences approach to evaluate household food security, it was discovered that exposure to the conflict is linked to notable declines in each of the three food security dimensions taken into consideration. Subsequent analyses quantify the roles of total resilience capacity and its distinct pillars, highlighting resilience capacity as an active mediator of the shocks. However, the mechanisms undermine households' long-term ability to endure shocks by dissipating a significant amount of resilience.

Using data on non-agricultural GDP and employment shares from the World Bank's World Development Indicators for the years 2000 to 2018, Adelaja et al. (2020) in their study found that resilience factors accelerate agricultural transformation and that armed conflict and terrorism-related shocks hinder structural transformation but not natural disasters. This suggests that although agriculture is frequently devastated in places afflicted by violence, the wider effects are even more detrimental to other economic sectors. Additionally, in research titled Armed Conflict and Food Insecurity: Evidence from Boko Haram's Attacks, George et al. (2019) In order to estimate the impact of Boko Haram, the General Household Survey (GHS) panel data for Nigerians with Boko Haram terrorist incidence from 2011 to 2016 was spatially joined. The results showed that an increase in conflict intensity, measured by the number of fatalities, increased the number of days when the household had to (1) rely on less preferred foods, (2) limit the variety of foods eaten, and (3) limit the portion size of meals consumed. A more serious indicator of food insecurity, the number of days households went without food, was unaffected. Conflict also has a negative impact on the Food Consumption Score.

In research conducted by Amaka Nnaji *et al.*, (2022) titled Farmer-herder conflicts and food insecurity: Evidence from rural Nigeria showed that both the incidence and the severity of farmer-herder conflicts significantly increase food insecurity, with the severity of these conflicts having a greater impact than their incidence. Primary data from 401 rural households were analyzed using a two-stage predictor substitution model to estimate the incidence and the severity of these conflicts. Further investigation shows that food insecurity, as determined by the number of days with few food options consumed, is positively and significantly impacted by the frequency and intensity of farmer-herder disputes.

Ogunniyi *et al.* (2016) in their research titled; Social Crisis, Terrorism and Food Poverty Dynamics: Evidence from Northern Nigeria, using 2010 Nigerian Living Standard Survey (NLSS) data, analyzed using descriptive statistics and ordered probit, ordering the households into three categories; food poor, moderately food poor and food non poor found that the mean food per capita expenditure (annually) was ₦25524.36 (\$128.23)¹. The survey also found that 84.85% of households in northern Nigeria—the bulk of which are rural, male-headed, and uneducated—are food poor. Additionally, the study discovered that the sect's actions had a detrimental effect on northern Nigerians' well-being and significantly exacerbate food poverty. However, it was discovered that initiatives like grants from international organizations like

UNICEF, WHO, World Bank, etc. improved the northerners' food security and decreased their food poverty.

Kelly (2016), in a research titled *A Decade of Change: Measuring the Extent, Depth and Severity of Food Insecurity* employing a series of indices adapted from the poverty literature to examine the depth and severity of food insecurity across the decade by race and ethnicity among low-income households with and without children found that the most rapid increases in the depth and severity of food insecurity were found among low-income households without children. Non-Hispanic White households with and without children had lower prevalence rates but steeper increases in the depth and severity of food insecurity throughout the decade. Non-Hispanic Black households with and without children were at the most disadvantaged among low-income populations.

According to the FAO (2017), conflict-affected countries have greater rates of food insecurity than countries that have not experienced violence. Violent conflicts can have a short-term impact on people's nutritional health. This, in turn, can have long-term implications for their livelihoods. Violent conflict has various implications for food security. However, at first, it must be stated that the influence of conflict on food security relies on what kind of conflict it is, given that assessing and categorizing conflict is not straightforward (Martin-Shields & Stojetz, 2019: 151). Studies show that the outcome depends on the type of conflict. Literature shows that conflict often occurs in rural areas, areas that have a lot of agriculture (FAO, 2017, p. 44). Consequently, violent conflict can especially impact agricultural production. On the one hand, food production can decrease. Cultivation is interrupted, where people depend on agriculture. Often fields were ruined by bombs, or it was simply unsafe to work on them (Baumann & Kuemmerle, 2016). Other times farmers abandoned their lands because farmers or workers were killed, people were forced to leave, fled voluntarily, or were involved in the fighting. This can lead to a labor shortage and therefore fewer people harvesting which then can lead to crop yield loss and food insecurity (Suthakar and Bui: 2020; Eklund, *et al.*: 2025; Adelaja *et al.*, 2019, p. 184). On the other hand, agricultural productivity can increase and have a positive impact on the food security situation in conflict areas.

Many empirical studies analysing the impacts of armed conflicts on food security focus on the effect of armed conflicts on the nutritional status of children, measured by anthropometric outcomes (Akresh, *et al.*, 2011; Akresh, *et al.*, 2012; Minoiu and Shemyakina 2014). Such outcomes, which include height-for-age Z-score (HAZ), weight-for-age Z-score (WAZ) and weight-for-height measures, are then directly linked to food insecurity (Martin-Shields and Stojetz, 2018). More direct measures of conflict-driven food insecurity include food expenses (Verwimp and Muñoz-Mora 2018), household consumption patterns (Serneels & Verpoorten, 2015), crop and livestock portfolios (Rockmore 2012), calorie intake (D'Souza and Jolliffe 2013) and farmers' investment decisions (Arias, Ibáñez and Zambrano 2018), while a few study which directly investigate the effect of armed conflict on dietary diversity includes Dabalen and Paul (2014), and Justin *et al.*, (2019). However, research on the impact of armed conflicts on agriculture and food production remain low in this region of the world (Martin-Shields & Stojetz, 2018). Arguably, the agricultural sector in many developing countries are particularly vulnerable to conflict. Recently emerged terrorist organizations have goals of controlling territories and establish parallel states in Nigeria, Somalia and Iraq (Adelaja and George, 2019). Furthermore, only a few studies have investigated the relationship between armed conflicts and food consumption (Adelaja and George, 2019; George, Adelaja, and Awokuse, 2021; George, Adelaja, and Weatherspoon, 2020).

To explore and address the stated problems of food security and food resilience, this study aims to specifically;

1. Determine the margin of food consumption diversity among the rural households
2. Determine the level of food insecurity among rural households.
3. Determine the resilience capacity of rural households to food security.
4. Identify the factors affecting rural households' resilience to food security.

1.1 Conceptual framework

There exists a direct relationship or effect between food security and food resilience. The higher the food security of a region, state, or household, the higher their resilience and vice versa. All efforts should be geared towards reducing rate of vulnerability, while enhancing resilience in order to attain a sustainable agricultural food supply, say Food Security (Rand 2023; Varrella 2021).

Fig. 1.0. Rural household food security resilience capacity and the determinant in conflict Zones.

Source: Author's Design.

Figure 1.0 showed how the variables are related to one another. It showed that rural household food resilience depends on the food security or insecurity degree of individual households. Which can be self-induced, Institutional based or naturally induced. Food insecurity means the households could not meet the minimum energy/nutrition intake vis-à-vis access, affordability and quality required for healthy life style while security means they can have sufficient food supply (Banger and Nwosu, 2020).

Food security defines access to affordable, safe and adequate food for healthy and active. Food insecurity affects the lives of millions of people around the world and is increasingly concentrated in conflict areas. Availability and access to food is a fundamental human right (WFP, 2021). Rural areas are characterized by numerous constraints that pose serious threats to their wellbeing (James *et al.*, 2022). Some of these factors include socioeconomic factors such as low education / literacy status, imbalance household structure which brings about poor household food and expenditure decision making; institutional factors such as insecurity manifesting in form of banditry and terrorism from groups or sects especially the prominent Boko Haram whose impact this study majorly focuses upon in relation to food security among the affected households (Batt 2022). Food resilience on the other hand is a derivative of food security which may imply a direct or indirect relationship in a downward or upward movement (FAO, 2017).

1.2 Impacts of Boko Haram Insurgency on Human food Security in Nigeria

Boko Haram insurgency has affected agriculture especially in some of the country's main food-growing areas. Yobe, Adamawa and Borno states worst hit by the insurgency are known to produce cowpeas, rice, millet, tomatoes, onions, yams, corns and sorghums, livestock and fish. Farmers are afraid to go to their farms as a result of fear of being attacked. A lecturer in the University of Maiduguri Abba Gambo said, No one can move a kilometre due to fear, most of them have fled their homes. According to the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugee, more than 1.5 million people, mostly farmers have been forced to flee their homes as Boko Haram intensified its insurgency in the past year. Also, the trade routes between the north east and the south are disrupted, hence making transportation and distribution of food very difficult.

The Central Bank of Nigeria stated that the disruptions on food distribution because of the insurgency are among the largest inflationary risks faced by the economy. *Eme et al* (2014) noted that Boko Haram has stopped the flow of beans. They further noted that two food items, pepper and tomatoes in particular, which mostly comes from the North and are used in most home is in short supply. Consequently, the prices of food have skyrocketed. According to Osagie (2013, p.24) if these violent attacks by the sect continue, it will plunge the country into a state of chronic food insecurity which is persistent and long-termed. The prices of food will continue to rise making it difficult for individuals and households to purchase sufficient and nutritious food for a healthy life. This will put individuals at the risk of hunger, starvation, malnutrition and even death. Malnutrition rates are high in areas worst hit by the insurgency and conflicts in general. According to the 2015 Humanitarian Needs Overview (2014, p.12), "a SMART Survey conducted by the national government and UNICEF in spring 2014 found GAM in Yobe states to be 15.5 percent and 13.6 percent in Borno state. Food and Nutrition insecurity are the fundamental threats to human security and the need to curb this insurgency cannot be overemphasized.

1.3 Food insecurity in protracted conflict situations

The causal linkages between conflict and food insecurity can be very complex. Food insecurity can both be a cause and a consequence of violent conflict. In recent complex conflicts, we also see environmental impacts restrict access to resources, which further creates tensions between

various groups. Experiences from Mali indicate how weather patterns and changing desert boundaries can lead to deadly conflicts between agricultural farmers and pastoralists. Nevertheless, causes of conflict can be a combination of various sources like political, institutional, economic, social and climatic stressors (Breisinger *et al.*, 2015). Lack of food might motivate people to engage in violent acts in the first place, combined with political and economic marginalization or other social grievances. A rebel group can promise to provide protection, food and shelter for recruits, using both material incentives in combination with ideological and political appeals as motivators of participation. However, food insecurity can also have an inhibiting effect on conflict. This is supported by evidence, because it is usually not the poorest or most food-insecure who participate in conflicts. For one, people without enough food must invest all their time and energy in order to obtain it, and may have reduced interest in pursuing political or ideological goals. Secondly, lack of food leaves little resources for the rebellious groups to exploit. They often depend on contributions from supporters or looting because they have no production of their own (Hendrix & Brinkman, 2013). Food insecurity may or may not be a driver of conflict in the first place, but conflict itself is a significant cause for food insecurity.

2.0 METHOD

2.1 Study area.

The study area of this research is Borno State, where the Boko Haram insurgency is based. Apart from the fact that the Boko haram sect has its origin in Maiduguri, majority of its members and followers resides in the town, with a strong suspicion of foreign membership from neighbouring countries of Chad, Niger and Cameroon (Halim, 2021). The members are alleged by United Nations to be involved in the gruesome killings, abduction and bombings in Maiduguri (UN, 2016). In a nut shell, Maiduguri appears to be the strong hold and spiritual centre of the BH sect. The sect s was known as early as in 2002, but assumed a dangerous dimension thereafter. However, this study is concerned with the period when the sect gained notoriety for killings and bombings that is from, July, 2009 to December, 2013 (Akinlade, 2015). The map of the study area is shown below

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Figure 2: Map of Nigeria showing the study area (Borno state)

The economy is largely agrarian, with 80% of the people dependent on agriculture for their livelihood, growing both food and cash crops (Tourism and Investment in Borno State, 2011). The state is also prominent for fishing and has great potentials for animal husbandry given the

large herds of cattle, sheep/goats and poultry that abound in its environment (Becam Business Environment Report, 2007).

2.2 Data Source.

Secondary data from General Household Survey (GHS), conducted by the Nigeria National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) in collaboration with the World Bank Living Standard Measurement Study- Integrated Surveys on Agriculture (LSMS-ISA) project, collected in 2018 was used for this research. The GHS-Panel survey is modelled after the Living Standard Measurement Study (LSMS) surveys, and it is representative of the rural and urban areas. The data contains household food consumption and food expenditure profile of the rural households in the study area, including all thirty-six states in the country and the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. However, this research will focus on the conflict affected states as described in the previous sections.

2.3 Analytical tools.

Appropriate descriptive and inferential statistical analyses of the data will be carried out using STATA, and or Excel analytical software in running the respective analytical tools on the data collected. Descriptive statistics such as Frequency, Sums, Maximum, Minimum, Mean, etc. will be used to present the data while Z-test, Household Hunger Scale (HHS), household food economy on food, and Gini coefficient, will be used to analyse and profile their food security level while Tobit Regression analysis will be used to determine other factors influencing their level of food security.

a. Test of Significance.

Unpaired treatment test (Z-test) was used testing for the significance of existing differences between two parameters for the hypothesized variables. It is expressed as follows;

$$\frac{M_2 - M_1}{\sqrt{SE_2 + SE_1}} \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

Where; M₁= Mean of first group, M₂= Mean of second group, SE₁= Variance parameters of category 1, SE₂= Variance parameters of category 2.

b. Household Food Expenditure.

While FAO worked hard to adjust, and or improve this measure or metric associated with food resilience and measure, the estimates remain out rightly sensitive to variations in methods. Given for example, the first estimate on the prevalence of undernourishment for year 1990, and assessed in 1992, it was 762 million, whereas when using today’s methodology (with the same underlying collected data) the estimation for 1990 is closer to one billion. Considering the current estimate, there has been a reduction in the number of individuals malnourished, whereas considering the former estimate, there has not (Caparros, 2014). Furthermore, macro-scale estimates are highly sensitive to these assumptions and methods used. Slight innocuous adjustments may lead to intricate differences in headline policy with implications, such as whether we are making progress or not in reducing food insecurity globally. This is considered problematic because measuring wide-scale progression is one of the few practical usages of such a measure, or metric (Joanna *et al.*, 2020.)

This approach focuses on the economic financial expenditure level of household on food, as a proxy for measuring level of food security and resilience. This principally adopts the Foster, Greer and Thorbecke (FGT) Foster *et al.*, (1984) forwarded a proposal for a group of poverty indicators, based upon a sole formula, that is capable to integrate any limit of concerns on

poverty via the “food poverty escape” parameter, “α” as used by Joanna *et al.*, (2020). This can be so denoted as “P-alpha Food poverty measure” or “the Food poverty gap index”:

$$P_1 = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^q \left(\frac{Z - y_i}{Z} \right) \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Z = the set food insecurity line, Q = the number of food insecure households, N= sum total of sample population, n= sum total of poor population, Yi = the household income, and α = FGT value, that assumes the values 0, 1 and 2, which is dependent on the incidence of concern on poverty. The bracketed amount is the proportionate income below the set poverty line. When we increase “α” the “aversion” to poverty as a measure of this index is raised. For example, when there exists zero poverty aversion, α = 2, the index is denoted as;

$$P_2 = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^q \left(\frac{Z - y_i}{Z} \right)^2 \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

Equation 3 equals to the poverty head count ratio and the index also measures the incidence of poverty. If the poverty aversion degree is increased such that when α = 1, the index will become or be denoted as;

$$P0 = q \frac{1}{N} = q \frac{H}{N} \dots\dots\dots(4)$$

Here, the head count ratio is the product of poverty-line and the income gap between the average poor person. The index estimates poverty depth and it is also referred to as the “income gap” or “poverty gap” index. The P₁ or the FGT index allows for a concern on the category of poorest of the poor by allocating more weights to poverty values of those of poorest category more above those slightly below the poverty-line. This can be calculated by squaring of the income gap so as to quantify the severity level of poverty;

$$P_2 = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^q \left(\frac{Z - y_i}{Z} \right)^2 \dots\dots\dots(5)$$

This measure fulfils the Sen’s transfer axiom which is required when a poor person transfers income is transferred to a poorer person, and it measures the poverty reduction level. Another benefit of this P-α measure is their state of decomposability. The overall poverty can be expressible as the product of the groups’ poverty share and weights of the entire population for each of the constituent group. Hence;

$$P\alpha = \sum K_j P_j$$

Where; J = 1,2,3 ... n groups, K_j= the population share for each category, while P_j= poverty measure for the individual groups. The per group addition to overall poverty C_j will then be measured. This measure would also provide for value of food consumed by households from farm output.

c. Household Hunger Scale (HHS)

The HHS is most appropriate to use in areas of substantial food insecurity. In those settings, the HHS can be used for a variety of objectives, including Monitoring the prevalence of hunger, Assess the food security situation, provide information for early warning, and inform standardized food security/ humanitarian phase classifications. The index ranges between 0-6 based on the responses on food consumption provided by the respective households. A household hunger scale can then be categorized based on the following Ballard *et al.* (2011); Little to no hunger in the household (0-1), Moderate hunger in the household (2–3), Severe hunger in the household (4-6).

d. Food access inequality.

To explore the margin of food insecurity level among the food secure and food insecure, the Gini coefficient will be used.

$$G = \frac{A}{A+B}$$

Where;

A= Population above the Lorenz curve i.e, Food secure category index

B= Population below the Lorenz curve i.e, Food insecure category index.

e. Determinants of the level of food insecurity.

I. Tobit regression

Due to the inconsistency, and biasness of the dependent variable in the least square estimate for the regression parameter having an upper and a lower limits, (Greene, 2012), this study employs a censored regression model, which is a standard Tobit model with a dualized limited categories of the dependent variables. An implicit function of the model is given as;

$$Y_i^* = X_i'\beta + \varepsilon_i \dots\dots\dots(6)$$

Where Y_i^* is the generated food security dependent continuous variable that assumes the value of 1 if $Y_i^* \geq 1$ and vice versa.

The structural forms of the dependent variable y_i is expressed as follows;

$$Y_i = \begin{cases} \varphi & \text{if } y_i < \varphi = 0 \\ \gamma & \text{if } y_i > \varphi < y_i' \\ y_i' & \text{if } y_i > \gamma = 1 \end{cases} \dots\dots\dots(7)$$

Where;

φ = lower limit,

γ , and y_i' = Upper limit.

The logarithmic likelihood explicit function of the model can be represented as follows, assuming that the error term, ε , dully obeys a normalized distribution with constant variance and mean; $0 \sigma^2 (\varepsilon \sim N(0, \sigma^2))$.

$$\log = \sum_{i=1}^N \left[I_i^\gamma \log \Phi \left(\frac{\gamma - X_i'\beta}{\sigma} \right) + I_i^\phi \left(\frac{X_i'\beta - \phi}{\sigma} \right) + (1 - I_i^\gamma - I_i^\phi) \left(\log \theta \left(\frac{y_i - X_i'\beta}{\sigma} \right) - \log \sigma \right) \right] \dots\dots\dots(8)$$

The Tobit analytical regression model was utilized to establish the relationships between the food security depth and the various influencing factors. The hypothesized independent variables are determinants of food insecurity among the farming households which are specified as follows:

$$Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \dots + \beta_{15} X_{15} + \mu_i \dots \dots \dots (9)$$

Where;

X₁ = Household Head’s age in years

X₂ = Cooperative membership (dummy; Yes=1; No=0)

X₃ = Size of Household

X₄ = Highest level of education in the household other than household head’s (years)

X₅ = Gender of household head (dummy; Male=1, Female=0)

X₆ = Farming experience level (in years)

X₇ = Dependency ratio (Dependent/Nondependents)

X₈ = Level of education of household head (years)

X₉ = Marriage status (dummy = 1, if married =0, if otherwise)

X₁₀ = Credit access (dummy; Yes= 1; No=0)

X₁₁ = Number of attack suffered this year

X₁₂ = Access to Electricity (dummy; Yes= 1; No=0)

X₁₃ = Farm Size (Hectre)

X₁₄ = Primary labour source (Dummy; Paid labor=1, Family Labor=0)

X₁₄ = Primary occupation

X₁₅ = Access to intervention/ palliatives

X₁₆ = Number of interventions per year

μ_i = Error term.

3.0 FINDINGS

3.1.1 Incidence of food insecurity among the respondents in the study area.

a. Food security status among the respondents in the study area.

The result of the analysis on food security status of the respondent in the conflict zone is presented in table one below.

Table 1: Distribution of incidence of food insecurity among the respondents in the study area.

Food security Status	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative
Food secure	90	56.52	90
Food insecure	70	43.48	160

Total	160	100.00
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Source: NBS; NDHHS, 2018-2019 Data analysis result.

Fig 3: Distribution of incidence of food insecurity among the respondents in the study area.

3.1.2 Food poverty indices of households in the study area.

The result of the analysis on food poverty level among the respondent in the conflict zone is presented in table two below.

Poverty depth	Food Poverty Index(P_a)	Headcount ratio (H)	Food insecurity index (P)
P_{a0}	1	0.4348	0.4348
Moderate poverty P_{a1}	0.4409897	0.4348	0.1917
Core Poverty (P_{a2})	0.6273416	0.4348	0.2728

Food poverty line= ₦ 6046.4; Food Poverty Gap= 53328.
 $\Pr(|T| > |t|) = 0.0466^{}$**

Table 2: Food poverty level profile among the households in the study area.

Source: NBS; NDHHS, 2018-2019 Data analysis result

Fig. 4. Food poverty level profile among the households in the study area.

3.1.3 Significance of difference between the expenditure-based food security level of food insecure and food secure households among the respondents in the study area.

The result of the significance of the differences in the food security weight of the food secure and food insecure households in the study area is presented in table three.

Table 3: Test for significance difference between the expenditure-based food security level of food insecure and food secure households among the respondents in the study area.

Variables	N	Mean (M)	Std.Error	
Food secure	90	13446.15	933.5001	
Food insecure	70	3380	340.2476	
Pooled	160	9069.565	920.9996	
Diff		10066.15	1107.807	Pr(T > t) = 0.0000***

Source: NBS; NDHHS, 2018-2019 Data analysis result.

3.2. Food insecurity inequality margin of respondents.

The result of the Gini coefficient analysis carried out to estimate the margin of the inequality between the food secure and food insecure household presented in table four below.

Variables	Food consumption	Inequality
Food Secure	349599.9	0.83796
Food Insecure	67600	

Table. 4: Exploring the margin of food insecurity level among the food secure and food insecure households.

Source: NBS; NDHHS, 2018-2019 Data analysis result.

3.3. Descriptive measure of food resilience.

A part Household Hunger scale (HHHS) descriptive analysis was conducted to describe the food security of the households in the study area as constrained by data and the result presented in table five below.

Table. 5: Distribution of Household Hunger among the respondents in the study area.

Household Hunger profile in last 30 Days.	Yes	No	Total
Q1: Household ever lacked food to eat due to lack of resources to get food?	57 (35.42)	103 (64.58)	160 (100)
Q2: Any household member went to sleep at night hungry because there was not enough food?	37 (22.92)	123 (77.08)	160 (100)
Q3: Any household member go a whole day and night without eating anything at all because there was not enough food?	23 (14.58)	136 (85.42)	160 (100)

Source: NBS; NDHHS, 2018-2019 Data analysis result. Percentage in Parenthesis.

Fig. 4: Distribution of Household Hunger among the respondents in the study area.

3.4. Determinants of the level of food insecurity among the respondents in the study area.

The result of the log-likelihood Tobit regression analysis on determinants of the level of household food insecurity in conflict zone is presented in table six below.

A maximum log-likelihood estimate analysis is a more variable encompassing yet, a robust estimator that suits determining the relationship between a continuous dependent variable, also well provides for binary dependent variable and their covariates. This study employed a binomial dependent variable Tobit regression function to analyse the determinants of food poverty depth among the households in conflict zone of North-East Nigeria.

The result of the Log-likelihood estimate on the determinants of food poverty depth among the households in conflict zone of North-East Nigeria is shown in table six below.

Table 6. Log-likelihood estimate analysis of the determinants of food poverty depth among the respondents.

Food poverty	Coefficient	Standard error	P> t
Gender	0.0752051	0.2376674	0.753
Age	0.0028011	0.0125962	0.825
Household Size	0.2676913	0.1337504	0.052**
Marital Status	-0.2638428	0.3241649	0.421
Years of Formal education	-0.0721608	0.0225476	0.003***
Access to aid	-0.9395477	0.3759962	0.017***
Constant	0.3998916	0.4242328	0.352
90 left-censored observations at Food poverty			Number of obs = 160
70 uncensored observations			LR chi2(6) = 35.34
0 right-censored observations.			Prob > chi2 = 0.0000
			Pseudo R2 = 0.3809

Source: NBS; NDHHS, 2018-2019 Data analysis result.

3.5 Discussion of findings.

3.5.1 Incidence of food insecurity among the respondents in the study area.

a. Food security status among the respondents in the study area.

The result of the analysis on food security status of the respondent in the conflict zone is presented in table [one](#) above. The result showed that about 44% of the household in the study area are food insecure.

b. food poverty indices of households in the study area.

The result of the analysis on food poverty level among the respondent in the conflict zone is presented in table [two](#) above.

The analysis of moderate poverty at P_{a1} showed that; 43% are food insecure, with an average food poverty intensity of 0.441 and also falls short of the population’s mean percapita food expenditure in the study area by 19%, while requiring a minimum of ₦53328 to break through their vicious food insecurity limit scourge. Further analysis on the severity of poverty (P_{a2}) showed that this 43% food insecure suffers an average food intensity of 0.6273 and also falls

short of the population's mean percapita food expenditure in the study area by 27%% at $P_{\alpha 2}$. This was found significant at 5% probability level. The food poverty headcount index of approximately 44% as found in this study shows a considerable level of reduction when compared to the 84% in year 2016 as found by Adebayo *et. al.*, (2025)

c. Significance of difference between the expenditure-based food security level of food insecure and food secure households among the respondents in the study area.

The result of the significance of the differences in the food security weight of the food secure and food insecure households in the study area is presented in table [three](#) above. The result showed that there exists a significant difference between the food security weights of food secure and food insecure households in the study area, and found significant at 1% probabilistic level. Due to the high level of significance, we can therefore proceed to compute a reliable food security inequality margin estimate for the entire population.

3.5.2 Food insecurity inequality margin of respondents.

The result of the Gini coefficient analysis carried out to estimate the margin of the inequality between the food secure and food insecure household presented in table [four](#) above revealed a high food consumption expenditure inequality margin of 0.83798 among the household in the study area.

3.5.3. Descriptive measure of food resilience.

A part Household Hunger scale (HHHS) descriptive analysis was conducted to describe the food security of the households in the study area as constrained by data and the result presented in table [five](#) above showed that there exists a considerable high rate of Hunger among the households in the study area. Since resilience has been incorporated into the food security literature as a legitimate component of vulnerability assessment that measures the ability of households to absorb the adverse impact of unforeseen shocks and still attain their wellbeing outcomes (Alinovi *et al.*, 2009; TANGO International, 2018), such as inability to afford meal in some acceptable quantity/quality against a given minimum standard as revealed in section 4.1 - 4.2 above, let alone not having anything to eat owing to deprivation of resources to procure food as revealed in section 4.3 below.

Sections 4.1 - 4.3 provides a considerable measure of the level of food resilience among the households in the study area.

3.5.4. Determinants of the level of food insecurity among the respondents in the study area.

The result of the log-likelihood Tobit regression analysis on determinants of the level of household food insecurity in conflict zone is presented in table [six](#) above.

A maximum log-likelihood estimate analysis is a more variable encompassing yet, a robust estimator that suits determining the relationship between a continuous dependent variable, also well provides for binary dependent variable and their covariates. This study employed a binomial dependent variable Tobit regression function to analyse the determinants of food poverty depth among the households in conflict zone of North-East Nigeria. The result of the Log-likelihood estimate on the determinants of food poverty depth among the households in conflict zone of North-East Nigeria is shown in table six below. The estimate has a R^2 of 38.1%, showing that the model predicts the estimates to an appreciable extent, given the set of explanatory variables in the model. The model's Prob > χ^2 is also significant at topmost probabilistic level.

The result shows that only three covariates are significant out of six variables hypothesized to influence food poverty in the conflict North East zone. Access to aid by household negatively influences food poverty, and significant at 1% probabilistic level with a coefficient of -0.9395477. This is likely due to the positive impact of disaster relief organizations that compliments the efforts of Government by providing disaster relief service to the inhabitants of conflict zones perhaps in form of cash, in addition to kindness. Furthermore, years of formal education was found to negatively influence food poverty, and found significant at 1% probabilistic level, in corroboration with Girma Gezimu Genre (2012). This is likely due to the fact that education helps provides a more informed financial decisions which in this case is not limited to consumption expenditure, while enhancing income earning opportunity, subject to the Keynesian theory of income, consumption and investment. This significance has a coefficient of -0.0721608.

Finally, Household size was found to increase food poverty, and found significant at 5% probability level, in corroboration with Girma Gezimu Gebre, 2012. This is likely due to the fact that larger households incur more on consumption expenditure to feed the households in their larger numbers, relative to smaller household sizes.

4.0 CONCLUSION, DISCUSSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This research study was conducted to determine the level of food insecurity, food resilience capacity, and the determinant factors among rural household in Borno State, Nigeria. From the research findings, it can be concluded that about 44% of the household in the study area are food insecure, with an average food poverty intensity of 0.441, while falling short of the population's mean per capita food expenditure in the study area by 19% at P_{a1} , and requiring a minimum of ₦53328 to break through their vicious food insecurity limit scourge, while further analysis on the severity of poverty (P_{a2}) showed that this 43% food insecure suffers an average food intensity of 0.6273 and also falls short of the population's mean per capita food expenditure in the study area by 27% poverty severity level P_{a2} found significant at 5% probability level.

Furthermore, the result of the significance of the differences in the food security weight of the food secure and food insecure households showed that there exists a significant difference between the food security weights of food secure and food insecure households in the study area, and found significant at 1% probabilistic level, providing a basis for a reliable food security inequality margin estimate for the entire population. The result of the Gini coefficient analysis revealed a high food consumption expenditure inequality margin of 0.83798 among the household in the study area. A part Household Hunger scale (HHHS) descriptive analysis was conducted to describe the food security of the households in the study area as constrained by data and it showed that there exists a considerable high rate of Hunger among the households in the study area.

The result of the log-likelihood Tobit regression analysis to determine the level of household food insecurity in the study area shows that access to aid by household negatively influences food poverty, while years of formal education was found to negatively influence food poverty, and both found significant at 1% probabilistic level respectively. Finally, Household size was found to increase food poverty, and found significant at 5% probability level.

4.1. Recommendations.

Based on the conclusion above, it can therefore be recommended that;

1. Government should prioritize increased annual budgetary allocation to the Agricultural sector of the economy in order to sufficiently boost quality agri-food production.
2. National palliative centres should be opened in each geo-political zone of the country, where food items would be stored, and sold to citizens during period of crisis such as conflict as it is been experienced in North-East Nigeria, so as to bridge food inequality gap.
3. Formal education should be encouraged owing to its significant effect in food poverty reduction.
4. Household heads should be orientated on maintaining healthy household size owing to its negative effect of food security and food resilience.
5. Insecure households with low resilience should be encouraged to join cooperatives.

4.2 Limitations of the Study.

Many of the limitations linked to this study is primarily that linked to insecurity, which limited the range of sample coverage in form of; frequency of accessibility, and, scarcity of respondents, amidst others. Also, the scope of responses of future survey should be improved in the questions, to expand workability of the data.

Conflict of Interest:

The authors declare no conflict of Interest

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